

¹H NMR and IR Spectral Studies on Organotin(IV) Substituted Oxinates*

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Several organotin(IV) chelates of the general type R_2SnL_2 ($R = CH_3, C_2H_5$ or C_4H_9 and $L =$ anion of a mono- or disubstituted 8-quinolinol) have been synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis, i.r. and n.m.r. spectroscopy. Studies of the infrared and proton n.m.r. measurements indicate that the diethyl bis(substituted-8-quinolinolato) tin(IV) chelates have *trans* octahedral structure. The variations in ligand and alkyltin proton magnetic resonance positions produced by chelation are examined and discussed.

NUMEROUS spectroscopic investigations concerning the bonding and structural characteristics of alkyl- and aryltin(IV) oxinates have been reported in recent chemical literature¹⁻⁹. However, spectral studies on dialkyl tin(IV) bis-substituted oxinates have received limited attention. Although the protons of the oxine molecule are not involved in metal coordination, consideration of changes in the chemical shifts for the ring protons upon chelation relative to their positions for the free ligand provide an insight into the nature of the metal-ligand bonds^{10,11}. This communication reports the results of our investigations on the structural aspects of some of the dialkyltin(IV) substituted oxinates by proton n.m.r. and i.r. spectroscopic methods.

Experimental

The infrared spectra of the compounds in Nujol mull were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Model 221 spectrophotometer. N.m.r. spectra were recorded on a Varian Associates Model T-60 spectrometer operating at 60 Mc/S with TMS as internal standard at room temperature (24°).

It was not possible to obtain the n.m.r. spectra of both the alkyl and 8-quinolinolato regions of every R_2SnL_2 complex because of the inadequate solubility of the compounds.

Reagent grade dimethylsulfoxide obtained from Riedel-de-Haën Ag Seelze-Hannover was used as the solvent for recording the n.m.r. spectra. *d*₆-DMSO was prepared by the method described by E. Bunel *et al.*¹². All the other reagents used were of A.R. grade.

The synthesis of the compounds bis(5-nitro-8-quinolinolato)dimethyltin(IV), bis(5-nitro-8-quinolinolato)diethyltin(IV), bis(5-nitro-8-quinolinolato)di-

butyltin(IV), bis(5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato)diethyltin(IV), and bis(5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato)diethyltin(IV) is reported elsewhere¹³. The mass spectral data of these compounds along with the data on dialkyltin(IV) dioxinates are also reported¹³.

Dialkyltin(IV) chelates 1 to 10 were prepared by following the general procedure outlined below. Solutions of dialkyltin dichloride (0.005 mole) in alcohol (10 ml) and ligand (0.01 mole) in DMF or alcohol (50-75 ml) were mixed together and refluxed for 4 to 5 hr. The mixture was cooled and the compound was precipitated by the addition of sodium acetate solution (1-2 g in 15 ml). The precipitates obtained were collected on a filter under suction, washed first with water and then with alcohol (ca. 5 ml) and dried.

1. Bis(7-nitro-8-quinolinolato)diethyltin(IV) :
Yield, 61.73%. Purified by recrystallization from methanol, m.p., 236°-38° (decomp.). Found: C, 48.23; H, 4.83; N, 9.72; Sn, 22.04%. Calc. for $C_{22}H_{10}N_4O_6Sn$: C, 47.62; H, 3.63; N, 10.09; Sn, 21.38%.
2. Bis(7-nitro-8-quinolinolato)dibutyltin(IV) :
Yield, 62.30%. Recrystallized from methanol, m.p. 149°-50°. Found : C, 50.98; H, 4.78; N, 9.31; Sn, 19.32%. Calc. for $C_{28}H_{28}N_4O_6Sn$: C, 51.15; H, 4.52; N, 9.1; Sn, 19.43%.
3. Bis(5,7-dinitro-8-quinolinolato)dimethyltin(IV) :
Yield, 90.82%, m.p., 328°-29°, decomp. Found : C, 39.05; H, 2.35; N, 13.93; Sn, 18.99%. Calc. for $C_{22}H_{14}O_{10}N_6Sn$: C, 38.95; H, 2.29; N, 13.93; Sn, 19.23%.
4. Bis(5,7-dinitro-8-quinolinolato)diethyltin(IV) :
Yield, 91.1%. m.p., 262°-63°. Found : C, 42.09; H, 2.58; N, 12.98; Sn, 15.80%. Calc. for $C_{22}H_{18}N_6O_{10}Sn$: C, 42.33; H, 2.31; N, 13.47; Sn, 16.14%.

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5. Bis(5,7-dinitro-8-quinolinolato)dibutyltin(IV) :
Yield, 91.2%, m.p., 253°–55°; decomp. Found : C, 44.62; H, 3.37; N, 11.68; Sn, 17.17%. Calc. for $C_{26}H_{26}N_6O_{10}Sn$: C, 45.10; H, 3.73; N, 11.90; Sn, 16.92%.
6. Bis(5-nitro-7-bromo-8-quinolinolato)dimethyltin(IV) :
Yield, 52.62%, m.p., 293°–94°. Found : C, 35.95; H, 3.08; N, 7.84; Sn, 16.99%. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{14}N_4O_6Br_2Sn$: C, 35.06; H, 2.05; N, 8.18; Sn, 17.34%.
7. Bis(5-nitro-7-bromo-8-quinolinolato)diethyltin(IV) :
Yield, 48.28%, m.p., 249°. Found : C, 37.78; H, 3.29; N, 7.61; Sn, 16.20%. Calc. for $C_{22}H_{18}N_4O_6Br_2Sn$: C, 37.06; H, 2.52; N, 7.86; Sn, 16.60%.
8. Bis(5-nitro-7-bromo-8-quinolinolato)dibutyltin(IV) :
M.p., 276°, decomp. Found : C, 40.23; H, 3.83; N, 7.48; Sn, 16.9%. Calc. for $C_{26}H_{26}N_4O_6Br_2Sn$: C, 40.52; H, 3.38; N, 7.28; Sn, 16.27%.
9. Bis(7-nitro-5-bromo-8-quinolinolato)diethyltin(IV) :
Yield, 84.44%, decomp. at 210°. Found : C, 37.38; H, 3.23; N, 7.52; Sn, 16.89%. Calc. for $C_{22}H_{18}N_4O_6Br_2Sn$: C, 37.05; H, 2.52; N, 7.86; Sn, 16.60%.
10. Bis(7-nitro-5-bromo-8-quinolinolato)dibutyltin(IV) :
Yield, 80.2%, m.p., 234°–35° decomp. Found : C, 39.46; H, 3.65; N, 7.52; Sn, 16.48%. Calc. for $C_{26}H_{26}N_4O_6Br_2Sn$: C, 40.52; H, 3.38; N, 7.28; Sn, 16.27%.
11. Bis(5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato)diethyltin(IV) : 5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinol (1.5 g., 0.005 moles) and diethyltin dichloride (0.6 g., 0.0025 moles) were dissolved together in alcohol and benzene mixture and heated for 5–10 min. Addition of sodium acetate solution (1–2 g. in 15 ml.) to this mixture resulted in the precipitation of the compound which was collected on a filter and dried. Yield, 1.4 g. (74.13%). It was purified by recrystallization from benzene, m.p., 209°–11°. Found : C, 34.41; H, 2.91; N, 3.85; Sn, 14.96%. Calc. for $C_{22}H_{18}N_2O_2Br_4Sn$: C, 33.82; H, 2.30; N, 3.60; Sn, 15.20%.
12. Bis(5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato) dibutyltin(IV) was obtained by following the same procedure for bis(5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato) diethyltin(IV). The compound obtained was purified by recrystallization from benzene, m.p. 208°–10°. Found : C, 37.52; H, 3.32; N, 3.38; Sn, 13.86%. Calc. for $C_{26}H_{26}N_2O_2Br_4Sn$: C, 37.29; H, 3.12; N, 3.35; Sn, 14.19%.

Results and Discussion

The proton nuclear resonance spectra of several diorganotin(IV) bis substituted oxinates and 5-substituted and 5,7-disubstituted-8-quinolinols are recorded

in different solvents and the data are given in Tables 1 and 2. In general, on complex formation, the alkyl groups attached to the tin, except in chelates, dimethylbis(5-nitro-8-quinolinolato)tin(IV) and dimethyl bis(5,7-dinitro-8-quinolinolato)tin(IV), exhibit shielding which is in agreement with an increased electron density on the tin via ligand donation. The marked deshielding observed when $R = CH_3$ in the chelates $(CH_3)_2Sn(5\text{-nitroOx})_2$ and $(CH_3)_2Sn(5,7\text{-dinitroOx})_2$ may be explained by assuming a *trans-R* arrangement which is necessarily perpendicular to the oxine rings. Free rotation would allow the CH_3 groups on the end of the alkyl chains and the intermediate CH_2 groups to reside above the cloud of heterocycle producing shielding, while a group directly attached to the tin would be in a deshielding area¹⁴. In addition, the normal inductive effect of the coordinating ligand and the magnetic influence of the tin atom also combine to govern the alkyl resonance position. Electron withdrawing substituents in the chelate ring also markedly deshield the CH_3 -Sn protons¹.

It is interesting to note that in the n.m.r. spectra of diethyl bis(substituted-8-quinolinolato)tin(IV) chelates examined, the protons of both the ethyl groups give just one resonance in CCl_4 and CS_2 solvents at room temperature. The dibutyl bis(substituted-8-quinolinolato)tin(IV) compounds, however, showed complex resonance pattern for the alkyl group which is similar to the one observed in the spectrum of uncomplexed dibutyltin dichloride. The singlet resonance pattern observed rather than the expected triplet and quadruplet spectra usually associated with an ethyl moiety is not sensitive to temperature changes in the range -20° to 28° . These chelates in solvents such as DMSO, however, exhibit the resonance lines associated with methyl and methylene groups. Harber and Gassenheimer¹⁵ have observed a single n.m.r. resonance for the ethyl groups in the compound $(C_2H_5)_3SnSCN$ in CCl_4 and acetonitrile solvents and explained that the observed resonance could be understood on the basis of accidental degeneracy of the methyl and methylene proton resonances rather than on the basis of a thermal averaging effect. On the basis of the identity of the absorption positions of the ethyl groups in the spectra of diethyl-bis(substituted-8-quinolinolato)tin(IV) chelates and i.r. data, it may be inferred that the two ethyl groups most probably occupy *trans*-coordination sites in the octahedral structure. This inference is also in accordance with the general tendency of hexa coordinated dialkyl tin derivatives to assume *trans*-alignment of the two alkyl groups¹⁴. The n.m.r. spectra of diethyl bis(8-quinolinolato)tin(IV) in CCl_4 and CS_2 solvents also exhibit a single resonance pattern for the ethyl groups. McFarlane *et al.*¹⁷ recently determined tin chemical shifts in ethyl tin compounds by $^1H\{-^{119}Sn\}$ double resonance experiments and observed a high field chemical shift for diethyl bis-(8-quinolinolato)tin(IV) and concluded that this is fully consistent with a six-coordinate monomeric octahedral structure (Fig. 1) involving coordination by nitrogen.

TABLE 1—PROTON MAGNETIC RESONANCE DATA

Compound	Solvent	Chemical shift positions(τ) R-group	
		CH ₃	CH ₂
1. (CH ₃) ₂ Sn(5-nitroOx) ₂	CF ₃ COOH	8.62(8.77)*	—
	CCl ₄	8.7 (8.8)	—
2. (CH ₃) ₂ Sn(5,7-dinitroOx) ₂	CF ₃ COOH	8.63	—
3. (C ₂ H ₅) ₂ Sn(Ox) ₂	CCl ₄	8.64(8.56)	8.64(8.21)
4. (C ₂ H ₅) ₂ Sn(5-nitroOx) ₂	CCl ₄	8.9	8.9
	CS ₂	8.93	8.93
	CH ₂ Cl ₂	8.87	8.87
	d ₆ DMSO	9.3	8.8
	CH ₃ CN	9.1	8.97
5. (C ₂ H ₅) ₂ Sn(5,7-dichloroOx) ₂	CCl ₄	8.87	8.87
6. (C ₂ H ₅) ₂ Sn(5,7-dibromoOx) ₂	CCl ₄	8.84	8.64
7. (C ₄ H ₉) ₂ Sn(Ox) ₂	CS ₂	9.5 (9.04)	8.64(8.19)
8. (C ₄ H ₉) ₂ Sn(5-nitroOx) ₂	CS ₂	9.17	8.79
9. (C ₄ H ₉) ₂ Sn(5,7-dichloroOx) ₂	CCl ₄	9.16	8.74
10. (C ₄ H ₉) ₂ Sn(5,7-dibromoOx) ₂	CCl ₄	9.17	8.77

Ox = anion of 8-quinolinol.

* Values in parentheses are for appropriate uncomplexed R₂SnCl₂ resonances.

 TABLE 2—PROTON CHEMICAL SHIFTS (τ) OF DIALKYL BIS-(SUBSTITUTED-8-QUINOLINOLATO) TIN (IV) CHELATES ALONG WITH 5- AND 5,7-DISUBSTITUTED-8-QUINOLINOLS IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Compound	Solvent						
		2-H	3-H	4-H	5-H	6-H	7-H
1. 5-Nitro-8-quinolinol	DMSO	0.87	2.17	1.05	—	1.5	2.9
2. (CH ₃) ₂ Sn(5-nitroOx) ₂	d ₆ DMSO	0.43	2.02	0.59	—	1.34	3.00
3. (C ₂ H ₅) ₂ Sn(5-nitroOx) ₂	-do-	0.48	2.10	0.61	—	1.42	3.14
4. (C ₄ H ₉) ₂ Sn(5-nitroOx) ₂	DMSO	0.37	1.99	0.53	—	1.32	3.00
5. 5,7-Dinitro-8-quinolinol	CF ₃ COOH	0.03	1.32	0.43	—	2.02	—
6. (CH ₃) ₂ Sn(5,7-dinitroOx) ₂	-do-	0.21	1.40	0.57	—	0.47	—
7. (C ₂ H ₅) ₂ Sn(5,7-dinitroOx) ₂	-do-	0.03	1.35	0.45	—	0.40	—
8. (C ₄ H ₉) ₂ Sn(5,7-dinitroOx) ₂	-do-	0.10	1.47	0.73	—	0.99	—
9. 5,7-Dichloro-8-quinolinol	DMSO	1.50	2.24	1.08	—	2.40	—
10. (C ₂ H ₅) ₂ Sn(5,7-dichloroOx) ₂	DMSO	1.42	2.17	0.77	—	2.30	—
11. (C ₄ H ₉) ₂ Sn(5,7-dichloroOx) ₂	d ₆ DMSO	1.47	2.27	0.50	—	2.07	—
12. 5,7-Dibromo-8-quinolinol	DMSO	1.60	2.30	1.08	—	2.08	—
13. (C ₄ H ₉) ₂ Sn(5,7-dibromoOx) ₂	DMSO	1.53	2.25	0.50	—	2.07	—
14. 5,7-Diiodo-8-quinolinol	DMSO	2.17	2.34	1.17	—	2.08	—
15. (C ₄ H ₉) ₂ Sn(5,7-diiodoOx) ₂	DMSO	1.60	2.27	0.67	—	2.07	—
16. 5-Nitro-7-bromo-8-quinolinol	AsCl ₃	0.97	1.97	0.60	—	1.00	—
17. (C ₂ H ₅) ₂ Sn(5-nitro-7-bromoOx) ₂	-do-	0.40	2.00	0.08	—	1.72	—

The proton magnetic resonance spectra of quinoline and several substituted quinolines have been reported^{10,18-20}. The chemical shifts observed for the ring protons in substituted-8-quinolinols (Table 2) are consistent with the shifts reported earlier. The corresponding resonances in the spectra of dialkyltin (IV) substituted-8-quinolinolates are sufficiently similar in appearance and field position to allow their identification. Electron donation to the tin on coordination has produced a deshielding of the

ligand protons, 2-H and 4-H in dialkyltin substituted-8-quinolinolates, the magnitude of which appears to be influenced by the inductive effect of the R-group. The 2-H and 4-H shift to low magnetic field compared to the resonance positions in the ligands in dialkylbis(5-nitro-8-quinolinolato)tin(IV) compounds and in compounds 9, 10, 11, 13, 15 and 17. The downfield shift of the protons may be attributed to strong interaction between Sn and N (in the ligand). The behaviour of 2-H can be explained by

a paramagnetic anisotropic effect of Sn-N bond of the substituted-8-quinolinolato ligand and to an intramolecular electric field and that of the 4-H by the latter effect²¹. The proton at position 6 (ortho

Fig. 1

to the nitro group) in dialkyl bis(5-nitro-8-quinolinolato)tin(IV) chelates is subjected to low field shift attributable to mesomeric effect. The 6-H resonance in tin(IV) chelates with 5,7-dihalo-8-quinolinols reported here is also deshielded indicating depressed electron density at C-6. This can arise from electron movement towards the metal atom through a (d-p) π overlap between the metals and the oxygen atoms²². The 4-H signals in dialkyl bis(5,7-dinitro-8-quinolinolato)tin(IV) shifted upfield indicating that the interaction between the metal and the ligand is not strong. When the interaction between tin and the oxinato ligand is not strong an upfield shift for the protons is reported by Yoshikane²¹.

The appearance of a single strong band in the region 550–580 cm^{-1} attributable to $\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{C})$ mode^{23,24} in the i.r. spectra of diethyltin(IV) chelates is consistent with a *trans*-R geometry and further supports the above structure assumed for these chelates. All the other dialkyltin(IV) chelates also show only a single $\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{C})$ band and the second $\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{C})$ band expected for compounds with *cis*-organic groups could not be located in the spectra. Okawara and his coworkers^{3,25} have indicated that Sn $\leftarrow$ N str. frequencies in organotin oxinates occur at ca. 395 cm^{-1} . The absorption bands in the region 400–380 cm^{-1} in the spectra of all the compounds have been therefore assigned to a tin-nitrogen str. frequency. The strong band observed in the region 640–650 cm^{-1} and at 445–450 cm^{-1} in the spectra of alkyl tin substituted oxinates have been assigned to $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OSnO})$ and $\nu_s(\text{OSnO})$ respectively on the basis of corresponding assignments in organotin oxinates²³. The frequency of the tin-oxygen str. mode is rather lower compared to the Sn-O bond in alkyltin alkoxides which has a covalent character²⁶. This may be due to the variations in the magnitude of interactions (d π -p π) between the ligand oxygen (in oxinates or substituted oxinates) and the tin atom.

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